

Maximizing Learning Outcomes for University-level ELT Learners doing ICT-based Oral Presentations

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ABSTRACT

Oral presentations are a common form of summative assessment in tertiary level English as a Foreign Language (EFL) syllabi. There will be an array of teaching and learning elements to be considered by a teacher in their set-up and execution of an ICT-based oral presentation activity that goes beyond having students stand in front of a class group and talk about a subject. Teaching effective oral presentation skills to university-level learners requires an understanding of how to maximize learning opportunities to persuasively convey a message orally and visually to an audience.

要旨

オーラルプレゼンテーションは、高等教育のEFLシラバスにおいて総括的評価の一項目としてよく用いられる。そのプレゼンテーションの形式として、視聴覚的なPowerPointなどの Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) がよく利用される。しかし、第二言語を学習している学生にとっては、クラスの前に立ち発表をするというタスクだけでも挑戦的であるが、ICTsを同時に準備・実行することは、更なる要素が加わることになる。つまり、教員にとって指導すべき教育的・学習的要素が増えると言える。大学生のプレゼンテーションは、聴衆に口頭だけでなく視覚的にも説得力を持って伝えることが要求される。教員はそれを指導する為に、学習をどう広げられるかを理解することが重要である。本稿では、高等教育でのPowerPointを活用したプレゼンテーションによる学習成果を効率化させる為の主な要素を見出し、討論する。

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

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INTRODUCTION

The maximization of learning outcomes from doing an ICT-based (Information and Communication Technologies) oral presentation is strongly influenced by both an EFL teacher's facilitation of a presentation activity and the learners' understanding of the presenter's role. This article identifies and details key considerations which can make the journey of doing an oral presentation a richer and more effective learning experience for teacher and learner alike.

TEACHER EXPECTATIONS

A presentation activity can be a valuable learning experience for learners and their teacher has a significant role to play in achieving this end. Presentation activities require a soundly structured and defined set-up in order for learners to gain maximum learning advantage.

Presentations provide an opportunity for learners to construct information and then communicate that information to an audience. It is important for a teacher to be clear about what is to be conveyed to the learners about assessment, structural requirements, and skills to be developed and mastered by the learners. Guiding questions can assist a teacher in organizing his/her expectations for the facilitation of a presentation activity, some suggestions include:

- What is the purpose of the presentation (informative, demonstrative, or persuasive)?
- What do I want my students to learn from doing a presentation?
- How can I best prepare my students to present?
- Do the presentation evaluation criteria match what is to be learned?
- Is each presentation to be done individually or in a group?

Pre-activity reflection can be used by a teacher as a mechanism to support student learning when preparing for and executing a presentation.

INTERACTIVITY IN AN ICT-BASED ORAL PRESENTATION

ICTs can be used to either transmit information in virtually a stand-alone mode or as an interactive aid for a presenter in order to convey information and respond to an audience. In the case of the latter, the role of a presenter may be thought of as a facilitator and, in part, a conduit for the flow of information between the ICT-based media and an audience. Using a PowerPoint slide presentation as one example of an ICT, a teacher can illustrate how an audience may view a presenter, and we can think about the relationship between a presenter, an audience, and ICT-based media as taking place via a flow of information, as suggested in Figure 1. Characteristically in this flow of information, a presenter can be viewed as

a facilitator of how an audience relates to information being shared through ICT-based media. At times, an audience may focus on a presenter or the slides but not on both at the same time. Looking at Figure 1, a presenter can use ICT-based media to maximize his/her communication with an audience. The audience receives information from the presenter's spoken communication and/or the slides. The audience members process the information and react. The presenter then observes any audience reactions and has the option to gauge appropriate responses, such as, providing more detail, clarifying what has been said, inviting questions from the audience, or moving on to the next part of the presentation. By viewing themselves as facilitators and conduits of a flow of information, presenters can utilize ICTs to a great advantage in reaching their audience.

Figure 1: Information Flow

Learner expectations about doing presentations can be shaped by past experiences of presenting or an absence thereof. Learners may have varied perceptions based on these experiences or a lack of them. Consequently, they may have worries about presenting in front of an audience. Anxieties may relate to language, performance, social considerations or other issues. In the case of using an L2, language anxiety can affect EFL learners when performing oral tasks. When EFL learners perform oral tasks, language anxiety issues arise as a result of communication apprehension,

social evaluation, and competition among learners (Cutrone, 2009; Hounsell & McCune, 2003). Furthermore, learner experiences of doing oral presentations can be influenced, specifically, by (Hounsell & McCune, 2003):

- prior experiences of presenting;
- teacher's guidance and support;
- learners' experiences of giving presentations and managing post-talk questions, comments and discussion;
- teacher's feedback;
- and learning from other learners' presentations.

However, through a teacher's facilitation of effective preparation, practice, and feedback, many anxieties that influence a learner's perception and performance of presenting can be managed.

TEACHER MODELING

Once the basic framework for the presentation activity has been set-up, then

the next step could be for the teacher to lead by example and show the learners how to conduct their presentation. If the teacher is confident that his/her learners are capable of performing based on their experiences of doing presentations and/or their sound oral proficiency in using English, then perhaps this step can be passed over. However, the teacher still needs to brief his/her learners carefully about key presentation points such as timing, structure, tips on using graphics, and core skills. Additionally, core skills can be practiced in classroom-based informal mini-activities. Honing presentation specifics such as eye contact, posture, gestures, volume and voice inflections, among others, can be done during class time with feedback provided by the teacher or other learners.

SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

Assessment criteria needs to be formulated and communicated to learners at the beginning of a presentation activity. As

evidenced in Table 1, this evaluation sheet guides teaching and learning objectives for a presentation activity. The establishment of clear assessment guidelines prior to learners preparing for their presentations enables the teacher to provide pre- and post-presentation feedback more effectively.

Feedback could be delivered in the form of constructive commentary in either paired or group settings. It can be advantageous to utilize the same structure and the same or similar skills categories so that learners can easily understand the evaluation criteria the next time they perform a presentation in class.

Table 1: Evaluation sheet

Name:			Topic:		Score total: 0 = poor 1 = average 2 = success	
Comments						
Comments & Timing	Posture	Visual Aids	Eye Contact	Gestures	Volume & Inflection	Questions & Answers
0 1 2	0 1 2	0 1 2	0 1 2	0 1 2	0 1 2	0 1 2

SUMMARY

There is a range of teaching and learning elements that require a teacher’s careful consideration for the set-up and execution of an oral presentation activity. The presenter’s role in maximizing the interactivity of the information flow from ICT-based media to an audience in oral presentations is also significant.

References

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